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MANAGEMENT AND EVALUATION OF PATIENT SATISFACTION TO HEALTH CARE IN THE PEDIATRIC CLINIC OF THE UNIVERSITY CLINICAL CENTER OF KOSOVO

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to reflect the real data with the approach of health services in the University Clinical Center of Kosovo and also have received different opinions from parents of children who have been hospitalized in the pediatrics clinic than they were satisfied with the provision of this clinical services offered.

Keywords: health management, evaluation of satisfaction of patients to health services, Pediatrics Clinic.

Introduction

Given that Kosovo health sector is a challenge of the present and the future, with this subject will be able to participate in the reform of the public health system, to understand systems European public health care, and implement practices best in the world, modern health possess to understand and articulate different approaches to moral issues, ethics and bio-ethics. Health policies will be introduced to the basics of crisis management, with processes and techniques for overcoming crisis situations.

Management and evaluation of patient satisfaction, understands prioritize strategies state of health, and the global politics of health through a mirror comparative cross-national on issues, concepts and main theories about planning, assessment, financing, the organization of health systems worldwide, management and personal care reform and health systems oriented population, leadership and global health actors. Health policies will be able to identify appropriate method of epidemiological health strategy, develop comprehensive and scientific hypotheses, test assumptions, learn to interpret data and take action.

Methodology

The study was conducted in the University Clinical Center of Kosovo pediatrics clinic. The study was prospective which is being conducted in the period from January to June 2016. In this work are surveyed all parents of children who have been hospitalized in the clinic.

Results

During this period, we interviewed 189 parents who have been hospitalized children in various clinical Repartee age was hospitalized children from 6 months to 5 years. 100 were female children and 89 male. 180 children were taken to direct survey of the parents while children 9 survey was done by the social worker because children have been abandoned. 10 of these children have been hospitalized children 2 times within this period.

Given that health Kosovo is a challenge of the present and the future and Kosovo health insurance still does not operate, during our survey to 170 surveyors have positive results which were satisfactory with the services provided by this clinic, while 19 Inquiry objections which we had demanded that the reimbursement of medicines in the hospital institutions of Kosovo should be 100%.

189 parents

100 of them female

89 of them male

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